

INTERFACIAL INTERACTIONS IN PU FOAM NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Structure development in cellular polyurethane - clay nanocomposites was studied. Flow micro-calorimetry was used to measure the interactions between the aromatic isocyanate and hydrated clays whilst forced-adiabatic IR spectroscopy was used to determine the effects of these interactions on the kinetics of copolymerisation and phase separation.

Keywords: nanocomposites, clays, interfacial interactions, structure development

INTRODUCTION

In this study, a pristine montmorillonite (MMT) intercalated with water is incorporated into a PU bulk copolymerisation, in which the intercalated water is utilised as a physical blowing agent during the formation of a flexible PU foam – layered silicate nanocomposite PLSN. A comparative material was also produced using an organo-modified clay (oMMT) containing a hydroxyl-functionalised modifier, reactive towards isocyanate. Flow micro-calorimetry (FMC) and FTIR were used to measure the interactions between an aromatic isocyanate and hydrated clays. The effects of these interactions on the kinetics of both copolymerisation and microphase separation during the formation of a cellular PU / MMT PLSN were determined by adiabatic temperature rise measurements and forced adiabatic FTIR spectroscopy.

EXPERIMENTAL

Foams

The polyurethane foams studied were formed via the reaction of toluene diisocyanate (TDI) with a mixture of a polyether polyol and de-ionised water acting as a chemical blowing agent. The polyol used was Alcupol F-4811 (Repsol Quimica), a triol of $M_n \approx 3,500 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ comprising predominantly polyoxypropylene repeat units with a few mol.% of polyoxyethylene units distributed randomly throughout the chain structure. The polyol/water mixture also contained an amine catalyst, N,N-dimethylethanolamine (ATOFINA), an organo-tin catalyst, dibutyltin dilaurate (Sigma-Aldrich) and a silicon surfactant, Tegostab B4900 (Degussa). The TDI used was Voranate T80 (Dow Chemicals), an 80:20 isomeric blend of toluene 2,4- and 2,6-diisocyanate. The sodium

Montmorillonite (Na-MMT) used, PGW (Nanocor), is a high-purity grade. Prior to use, PGW was dried at 140 °C for at least 3 hours which reduced its water content to ≤0.3 wt.-%. Three foams were produced, namely; an unfilled foam (designated as UF) and two PLSN foams, based on the same formulation but containing 5 and 10 wt.-% Na-MMT (designated as P5 and P10, respectively). The required amounts of Na-MMT (17.38g or 36.68g for P5 and P10, respectively), polyol (200g), water (9.8g), silicone surfactant (2.2g) and amine catalyst (0.5g) were weighed and mixed in a sealable glass container. The mixture was then subjected to 50-60 Hz ultrasound waves (Precision Ultrasonic, Ultrawave) for 2 hours at 60 °C. The intercalated polyol/water/Na-MMT mixture was then placed in a 900 ml polypropylene beaker and stirred at 3000 rpm for 10 s using a Multifix 4000 mechanical agitator. Tin catalyst (0.28g, as a 10 wt.-% solution in polyol) was added and the mixture stirred for another 10 s. Finally, the TDI required to give a system stoichiometry of 1.07 (117.3g) was added and the reactant mixture was stirred for a further 10 s before being poured into a mould (a standard laboratory-scale cardboard box, 310 x 150 x 150 mm) to allow *in-situ* polymerisation to form the PU foam nanocomposite.

2.2 Techniques

Adiabatic temperature rise (ATR) measurements were carried out over 1200 s using two thermocouples (Omega Eng. Inc.) positioned at the midpoint of the mould. Temperatures were recorded as a function of time and at a frequency of 1 Hz via a Macintosh[®] PC equipped with Strawberry Tree ACM-12-8 data acquisition hardware and a Workbench[™] V3.1 software package. The rapid reactions occurring during PU foam formation and their associated exotherms, together with the self-insulating nature of the developing foam, result in quasi-adiabatic temperature conditions. The resultant temperature-time (ATR) profiles were corrected for small heat losses using the following equation:

$$T_{t,corr} = T_t + \frac{U}{\rho C_p} \int_0^t (T_t - T_{amb}) dt \quad (1)$$

where C_p and ρ are the specific heat capacity and density of the PU, respectively, T is the temperature, t is the reaction time and U is the heat transfer coefficient per unit volume.

Forced-adiabatic Fourier transform-infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was conducted in attenuated total reflectance (a.t.r.) mode. For each foam formulation, the ATR heating profile was calibrated before being applied to the FTIR reaction cell containing a ZnSe crystal. The cell was placed between the infrared generator and the receiver in a FTIR spectrometer (Impact 410, Thermo Nicolet). A 1 cm³ sample of the liquid reaction mixture was poured onto the crystal surface, and the infrared data were collected at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, co-adding 4 scans per spectrum: the total time per spectrum was 2.2 seconds. The temperature of the FTIR reaction cell was recorded as a function of time at a frequency of 1 Hz via two type-J single-wire thermocouples, positioned adjacent to the ZnSe crystal in the cell. The FTIR data were corrected for baseline and a.t.r. geometry effects and analysed using Omnic[®] software (Nicolet Instrument Corp.) to give FTIR absorbance versus time profiles. All spectra were normalised relative to the methyl stretching peak at approximately 2960 cm⁻¹.

The penetration of a monomer into the gallery spaces of MMT may be considered an adsorption process which can be studied by flow micro-calorimetry

(FMC). FMC has proved to be a useful tool for characterisation of filler surfaces, in terms of their surface chemistry and their interaction with surface treatments, in that both the heats of adsorption/desorption and the amounts of a probe molecule adsorbed and desorbed can be determined. The FMC apparatus used was a Microscal 3V linked to a Microscal thermomistor bridge/control unit whose output was fed to a Perkin-Elmer 900 series interface. The cell outlet was connected to a Waters 410 differential refractometer, whose data was fed into the second channel of the 900 series interface. The 900 series interfaces were linked to a PC for data manipulation using PerkinElmer Chromatography software (TotalChrom Version 6.3.1). For FMC studies, Na-MMT conditioned in ambient humidity (non-dried) and dried (140 °C for 3 hours) Na-MMT were used. The probe, 4-ethylphenylisocyanate, 4-EPI (Sigma-Aldrich), is an aromatic monoisocyanate and is therefore representative of the aromatic diisocyanates typically used in the commercial production of PU. Adsorption/desorption of 4-EPI from heptane solution (0.2% w/v) was conducted using a cell temperature of $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and a solvent flow rate of $4.0 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ hr}^{-1}$. Decahydronaphthalene was used as the non-adsorbing probe. A sample ($98 \pm 1 \text{ mg}$) of Na-MMT was placed in the FMC cell and left to equilibrate overnight at a heptane flow rate of $0.3 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ hr}^{-1}$ after which the flow rate was increased to $4.0 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ hr}^{-1}$ and the system left to settle for approximately 1 hour. Data collection was then started and after 5-10 minutes the inlet was switched from pure solvent to the 4-EPI solution. After the refractive index data reached a stable limiting value (typically 120 to 150 minutes) the inlet was switched back to pure solvent and the desorption process recorded. The amount adsorbed was determined by normalization of the refractometry data deflection for the non-adsorbing probe to that for the adsorbing probe. Using an identical approach, the amount of probe desorbed can also be calculated. After completion of the adsorption/desorption cycle the sample was removed from the cell and dried at 70°C for 20 hours.

Infrared spectroscopy of the Na-MMT samples, recovered from the FMC cell and dried as outlined above, was carried out using diffuse reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (DRIFTS). A Spectra-Tech DRIFTS cell was fitted to a Thermo-Nicolet Nexus FTIR bench and purged with water- and CO_2 -free air at 20 l min^{-1} . The Na-MMT samples were diluted to 5 wt.-% in finely ground KBr using a micro spatula. Absorbance spectra were made up of 164 scans with resolution set to 4 cm^{-1} . In order to more effectively highlight IR bands associated with adsorbed species, spectral subtraction was carried out using solvent-washed Na-MMT as a reference (i.e. Na-MMT that had been washed with heptane in the FMC cell and dried in the same manner as the samples).

WAXD was performed in reflection mode using a Philips X'pert PRO MPD. Using an incident X-ray wavelength of 0.1542 nm , WAXD data were obtained between a range of scattering angle (2θ) of $1^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 30^\circ$ with a step size of 0.05° and a scan rate of $0.3^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$. For the foams, specimens of approximately $20 \times 17 \times 10 \text{ mm}$ were cut from the cores of the foam buns. For the Na-MMT samples recovered from the FMC cell, each sample was evenly distributed onto a thin layer of silicone grease spread over a silicon wafer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FMC and FTIR were used to monitor the adsorption process and any chemical reaction between dried and hydrated MMT and a model monoisocyanate; 4-ethylphenyl

isocyanate (4-EPI). Results¹ indicate that in a PU-foam reaction mixture the water will tend to associate with the MMT. Upon reaction with isocyanate, the presence of the MMT both promotes the formation of urea and generates urethane linkages between silicate lamellae and the polyurethane.

The decay in the intensity of the NCO absorption band at 2270 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1) was used to monitor the conversion of TDI functional groups, and the results confirmed that the rate of polymerisation increases with increased MMT content. The kinetics of microphase separation between poly(ether-urethane) soft segments and polyurea hard segments were obtained from the carbonyl regions of the mid-infrared spectra that were used to monitor the evolution of soluble urea ($\sim 1711\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and hydrogen-bonded bidentate urea ($\sim 1639\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The evolution of soluble and hydrogen-bonded ureas for an unfilled foam is shown in Fig.2.² Soluble urea is formed initially and its concentration increases steadily during foam formation. The microphase separation transition (MST) is defined as the onset of rapid evolution of hydrogen-bonded urea.

Figure 1 Decay of the NCO absorption at 2270 cm^{-1} with time for an unfilled system (F0) and foams containing 5 and 10 wt% of MMT (F5 and F10, respectively)

Figure 2. The development of soluble and hydrogen bonded urea structures with time, showing the microphase separation transition time for an unfilled foam.

Studies with MMT and oMMT showed that strong interactions between the clays and the urea hard segments can severely restrict the formation of hydrogen bonded urea.

References

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